

Public Open Space Design Concept in the Historic Area of Rengasdengklok

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Abstract:- Public open spaces in a city are generally in the form of a town square located in the city center, where the local government offices and other supporting facilities are located. The town square as one of the public open spaces in Rengasdengklok City is unique, in addition to being the center of community activities, it is also located in the same area as cultural heritage buildings. This is what makes the Rengasdengklok City square have characteristics that display the city's identity. The purpose of this study is to examine the current condition of Rengasdengklok City's public open spaces, through an analysis that links the concept of environmentally friendly and sustainable public open spaces and considers economic, social and cultural aspects. The research method used is a qualitative descriptive method, to describe and analyze the actual conditions of the objects studied by identifying the potential and existing problems. The results of the study show that the public open space in this location has not functioned optimally in terms of environmental factors, infrastructure and its relationship to city assets. It is hoped that through this research, public open spaces can be developed into ideal spaces for various activities and contribute to increasing the value and quality of the historical area of Rengasdengklok City.

Keywords:- Cultural Heritage, Concept, Public Open Space, Rengasdengklok

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Rengasdengklok is one of the sub-districts in Karawang Regency, located in the northern part of West Java Province. Rengasdengklok is known as the city of the origin of Struggle, with historical events leading up to independence. On August 16, 1945, the young fighters temporarily exiled President Soekarno and Vice President M. Hatta to hold negotiations to accelerate the proclamation of independence. In a house owned by a local resident [1]. The house where the refugees were taken was preserved as a "Historical House" and as a commemoration of the event, in 1950 a struggle monument was built called "Tugu Kebulatan Tekad".

These two buildings are included in the criteria for cultural heritage [2]. Another building that is a cultural heritage is the Kawedanaan Office [3]. Built around 1920, with a building form that has a typical West Java vernacular architecture. This building was the place where the Red and White flag-raising ceremony was first held, namely on August 16, 1945 [4]. At that time the building was a regional administrative office, after independence it was converted into a regional government office, namely the sub-district office located on Jalan Pasar Rengasdengklok.

The three cultural heritage buildings are located in urban areas, namely in North Rengasdengklok Village and South Rengasdengklok Village. In line with the development of the city, the Rengasdengklok urban area has experienced changes and improvements in development so that it requires existence by having a more representative regional government office. In 2011, a new sub-district office was built, located on Jalan Perintis Kemerdekaan Number 1 [5], South Rengasdengklok Village, which is the city center or capital of Rengasdengklok. The location of the new sub-district office is about 1200 meters from the old office.

As in most areas in Indonesia, the central area of Rengasdengklok City has a public open space in the form of a town square, in this case the town square that was formed in line with historical events that occurred in Rengasdengklok City, is important because it is located in an area where there are historical buildings that are cultural heritage. Rengasdengklok City Square has a close relationship with historical buildings, not only because of its location but also its function and symbolism. Historical buildings have high historical and cultural value and the square is an integral part of these historical buildings. The relationship between the square and historical buildings strengthens the city's identity and becomes a unique cultural symbol by highlighting the meaning of space and accommodating cultural activities within it [6].

B. Problem Formulation

➤ *The Problem Formulation is Described based on Several Things, Namely:*

- Is the town square currently functioning optimally to support various community activities?
- How can the town square be utilized by the community for economic, social, cultural activities, and maintaining the environmental ecosystem, as well as supporting the existence of cultural heritage buildings around it?

C. Research Objectives

The purpose of the research is to determine the extent to which the Rengasdengklok city square as a public open space can support the existence of the city center area and cultural heritage buildings, by examining the available facilities, the use of space, the aesthetic appearance of architecture and its environment.

D. Benefits of Research

The benefits of the research are to provide direction as a basis for the development of physical facilities and infrastructure by conceptualizing the design of public open spaces that can meet the needs of the government and the community as users by linking the concept of green open space with economic, social and cultural aspects.

E. Scope of Discussion

➤ *The Scope of Discussion Consists of Several Main Topics, Namely:*

- Identifying characteristics based on criteria, functions and quality of public open spaces through a study of policies and basic principles of urban and environmental planning
- Identifying the needs of the government and society that are oriented towards promoting historical tourism, availability of facilities, improving environmental quality for the welfare of its people
- Conceptualizing the design of the town square as a public open space and its relationship to city assets

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The definition of public open space is external public space, internal public space and external and internal quasi public space [7]. One that is related to the theme of the writing is about external public space which is defined as an outdoor space that can be freely accessed by the public to carry out activities and social interactions, for example public fields, town squares, plazas, pedestrian areas, highways, city parks, recreational parks and so on [8].

- The basic criteria for public open space are:
- Responsive: can be used for various activities and interests
- Democratic: can be used by various groups
- Meaningful: has interactions between humans and the environment

Public open space must be able to provide a conducive environment so that the interactions of different users can be met properly. The use of public open space is divided into 2 aspects [7], namely:

- Active use in the form of direct use of activities such as playing, relaxing, exercising, interacting and so on
- Passive use in the form of use to observe the environment such as research, observation and so on.

Public open spaces are closely related to green open spaces divided into public green open spaces (such as city parks, green lanes), and private green open spaces (such as home yards, parks owned by agencies), both of which have main functions [9], namely:

- Provision of open spaces as microclimate regulators that ensure the natural air and water circulation system will run smoothly
- As shade, windbreak and oxygen producer
- As rainwater absorbers and filters for air, water and soil pollutants
- As a habitat for various animals
- Has social, cultural, economic, recreational and aesthetic functions.

Public open spaces have various functions, to optimize these functions what is needed is:

- Physical assets. Providing facilities that can meet the needs of the community with good quality, complete and safe, such as sports facilities, children's playgrounds and so on
- Architectural and ecological. Must be able to provide environmental beauty for the surrounding environment and contribute to environmental comfort by creating a green and cool environment so that it can maintain the balance of the environmental ecosystem in urban areas
- Social, cultural and economic. Can accommodate various social, cultural and economic activities of the community by developing activities for the community to gather, interact and organize cultural activities and buying and selling arenas such as exhibitions, bazaars, street vendors and so on
- Emergency function. Providing a place that functions as an emergency first aid place and evacuation place in case of disaster

The quality of public open space concerns several things, namely:

- Public open space must have good physical environmental conditions, such as comfortable, well-maintained gardens, adequate facilities and easy access
- Have interesting activities for visitors
- Have a container that allows the community to interact socially
- Have a close relationship with the community as users of facilities and those authorized as managers

Public open space must meet several criteria [10]:

- Easily accessible location and easy transportation
- As a public space, can be used for various activities and social interaction
- Beautiful and aesthetic architecturally
- Safe and comfortable location
- As a place to express art and culture

Public open space design is related to the design of the city (area) as a whole which includes spaces between buildings, spaces created for the community related to the potential and physical quality of the environment. The elements contained in the area include land use, building form and mass, circulation and parking, open space, pedestrian paths, supporting activities, maintenance and preservation [11].

Cultural heritage can be utilized for culture and tourism [1]. The development of cultural heritage areas can become attractive tourist attractions by considering several things, namely:

- Improving the image of the area by displaying the beauty of the environment and expanding green open spaces
- Maintaining cultural heritage buildings and their environment
- Providing tourism facilities such as restaurants, culinary places, souvenir shops, and lodging
- Developing history education, arts and culture activities for the community
- Improving environmental infrastructure such as road networks, pedestrians, transportation
- Creating environmental security and comfort

III. RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, the method used is a qualitative method, which is a study that focuses more on describing

the condition, nature or essence of a particular symptom or the value of an object. This study carries a concept and recommendation proposal. This qualitative research method aims to describe more clearly the problems that exist in the Rengasdengklok city square, providing space for a research process that is closer to the object of research.

Descriptive research method, is a study that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from a resource person or behavior that can be an object of observation. This explanation focuses on the type of data collected in the research process, namely qualitative descriptive.

A. Data Collection Technique

The data collection technique used is a descriptive qualitative analysis approach, to make it easier for researchers to study and observe more carefully and then be able to explain and summarize various types of data obtained in the form of collecting visual data in the form of location surveys, object photos and satellite photos, interviews with several resource persons and collecting information from literature data, journals and related articles to identify the potential and problems in the square.

B. Data Analysis

Data analysis is the process of collecting, reviewing and compiling data that has been carried out by researchers, then the analysis is carried out by connecting several aspects related to the town square as a public open space, both economic, social, cultural and environmental ecosystem aspects. The town square is important for Rengasdengklok City because it has a uniqueness with the existence of historical buildings, so that it can represent a public open space that supports the existence of the city's assets. Based on the data collected, a concept for designing an area can be made in order to achieve an area that has optimal function and architectural aesthetics that displays the identity of Rengasdengklok City.

C. Research Location

The location of the research is Rengasdengklok City, which is one of the sub-districts in Karawang Regency, in the northern part of West Java Province. Rengasdengklok District, which is located on the north coast of Java Island, is in the lowlands with an altitude of 7.90 m above sea level and has a tropical climate. The distance from Rengasdengklok District to the capital of Karawang Regency is around 20 km.

Fig 1: Location of Rengasdengklok City
Source: Tribunnews.com, 2020

Fig 2: Rengasdengklok District Area
Source: Karawang Regency Government, *nd*

➤ *Rengasdengklok District consists of 9 sub-districts:*

- Dewi Sari Sub-district
- Kertasari Sub-district
- North Rengasdengklok Sub-district
- South Rengasdengklok Sub-district
- Amansari Sub-district
- Dukuhkarya Sub-district
- Karyasari Sub-district
- Kalangsurya Sub-district
- Kalangsari Sub-district

➤ *City assets located in the Rengasdengklok urban area are:*

- In North Rengasdengklok Village, namely cultural heritage: Historical House and Monument of Struggle, Tugu Kebulatan Tekad.
- In South Rengasdengklok Village, namely the Rengasdengklok District Office and the Kawedanaan Office (cultural heritage)

The facilities and infrastructure in the Rengasdengklok urban area are: schools, health centers, places of worship (mosques and churches), residential areas, shops, stalls, cemeteries and so on.

Fig 3: Rengasdengklok Urban Area
Source: Google Earth, Processed 2024

➤ *Caption:*

- Town square
- District Office
- Struggle Monument Tugu Kebulatan Tekad
- Historical House
- Kawedanaan Office

The focus of the research is the town square located in the central area of Rengasdengklok City, namely in South Rengasdengklok Village. The land area is around 2.4 hectares, with the following boundaries:

- North : Jalan Raya Tugu Proklamasi
- East : Jalan Alun-alun
- South : Jalan Alun-alun
- West : Jalan Alun-alun

Fig 4: Town Square Area
Source: Google Maps, Accessed 2024

D. Research Location

The research was conducted by analyzing how the town square plays a role in the historic area, its potential and utilization. Preparation of research reports based on

the results of location surveys, photo attachments and literature studies to be able to see existing problems, which can then be used to create planning concepts for the development of the town square and the historic area.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

A. Existing Condition of Alun-alun

Existing Condition

Main Entrance

- Main access to the town square
- Unattractive appearance

Proclamation Monument

- Focal point in the town square
- Unattractive shape and appearance
- Poorly maintained condition

Open Field

- Ceremonial area and volleyball sports field
- Almost all of the site is paved (paving block)
- Unsuitable condition, damaged and dirty

Existing Condition

Park

- The park area is only planted with grass, there has been no garden arrangement
- Greenery is only around the fence of the town square
- It looks hot and dry

Street Vendor Kiosks

Kiosks are not arranged, occupying almost every corner of the town square
It looks dirty and shabby

Supporting Facilities

- No security post
- No public toilets
- No facilities for the disabled
- No facilities for arts and culture performances
- No children's playground
- Lack of park elements such as park benches, lighting, trash bins and so on
- Inadequate parking space

Fig 5: Condition of the Square

Source: Personal Photos and Analysis, 2024

B. Public Open Space Parameters (Square) of Rengasdengklok City

Based on the characteristics, criteria, functions and quality of the town square, the design concept that needs to be developed in the public open space of Rengasdengklok City is based on government policies and the principles stated in the Literature Review (Chapter 2), namely:

➤ Image

This means it is important to provide an identity through an aesthetically attractive physical appearance.

➤ Accessibility

Strategic location, easily accessible and recognizable.

➤ Access and Equality

The space can be used by everyone.

➤ Function and Meaning

Has various functions and has an implied meaning in the space.

➤ Physical Assets

Provides facilities that can meet the needs of the community with good quality, complete and safe.

➤ Architectural and Ecological

Provides beauty and environmental comfort, contributes to maintaining the balance of the urban environmental ecosystem.

➤ Social, Cultural, Economic and Recreational

Can accommodate various social, cultural, economic and recreational activities.

➤ Emergency Function

Providing a place that functions as an emergency evacuation site in the event of a disaster.

➤ Supporting Elements

Available supporting elements for activities and park elements.

➤ Synergy

There is connectivity with city assets in the area.

C. Design Concept of Rengasdengklok City Square

Rengasdengklok City Square is related to historical buildings and local government offices. In its development, it requires integrated and sustainable area planning, in order to support the existence of the square as a symbol and landmark that forms the image and identity of Rengasdengklok City. The formation of the area needs to be supported by the provision of adequate facilities and infrastructure as well as the preservation and development of city assets, so that a more representative and meaningful area is created.

A. Square Area

Development of the square area towards existing assets and supporting facilities, namely:

- Historical buildings which are cultural heritage as the main assets for the development of wider historical tourism destinations.
- As a tourist attraction, cultural heritage buildings need attention from competent parties and community contributions are needed so that the area is controlled and well maintained
- Facilities and infrastructure to support the town square area such as land use, accessibility and connectivity between buildings, road networks, circulation and parking,
- Supporting facilities for economic activities (eateries, culinary, souvenirs), social (sports, recreation), culture (arts and culture, local wisdom), environment (green, beautiful and comfortable).

Fig 6: Connectivity in the Square Area
Source: Personal Analysis

B. Square

The design concept for public open spaces that are the focus of this study, then several things that need to be considered are:

Table 1: Design Parameters for Alun-alun Elements

Parameters	Physical Elements
Image Function and meaning	Main Entrance: Gate As the main access to the square, an aesthetic appearance is needed, the gate element is made as a gateway that reflects the identity of the Rengasdengklok City square
Image Function and meaning	Proclamation Monument: Focal point Located in a central position, has a meaning as a symbol of historical events
Parameters	Physical Elements
Image Function and meaning	Open Field: Flagpole and ceremonial place Provision: - Paved land for ceremonies, can function for other activities
Accessibility	Provision: - Road network, sidewalks - Transportation
Access and equality	Used by all members of society, children, the elderly, the disabled
Physical assets	Provision: - Sports field - Children's playground - Seating
Architectural and ecological	A beautiful and comfortable place: - Greenery with shady trees - Beautiful garden
Economic, social, cultural	Provision: - Street vendor kiosk area - Area for sports and recreation

	- Area for performing arts and culture, exhibitions, bazaars, cheap markets
Emergency function	Provision: - Temporary evacuation in case of disasters such as floods, fires and so on
Supporting elements	Provision: - Security post - Public toilet - Parking lot - Disabled facilities - Park elements (park benches, lighting, trash bins)
Synergy	Connected to cultural heritage buildings

➤ *Precedent Study:*

Illustration

Bangil-Pasuruan City Square Gate
Source: detiktravel, 2016

Surabaya Bambu Runcing Monument
Source: tempatpopuler.com, 2024

Purwodadi City Square Ceremonial Field
Source: adminPIKP,2024

Illustration

Tebet Eco Park, Jakarta
Source: terasplus.id, 2024

Pancasila Square Parking Area, Kebumen
Source: koranbernas.id, 2024

Disabled Facilities, Bungkul Park Surabaya
Source: SurabayaNetwork.id, 2023

Street Vendors, Bandung Square
Source: pikiran-rakyat.com, 2024

Fig 7: Illustration of Elements in the Square

Fig 8: Layout of Elements in Rengasdengklok Square
 Source: Personal Analysis

➤ *Caption:*

- Main Entrance
- Parking area
- Open field
- Proclamation Monument
- Park and greenery
- Street Vendor Area
- Sports field (volleyball, basketball)

- Realizing connectivity between buildings with spatial planning in the historical area
- Further developing facilities in the town square related to the economic, social and cultural activities of the local community
- Creating an area that supports environmental preservation and ecosystems
- The active role of government, non-government and the community in the management and maintenance of the area

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

The public open space of Rengasdengklok City is a town square that developed in line with historical events leading up to the independence of the Republic of Indonesia. Its existence is associated with the existence of historical buildings, so that it becomes the identity of Rengasdengklok City. The use of the town square as a place for ceremonies, a place for people to socialize, exercise, recreation and function as an emergency in the event of a disaster. From the results of the study, the town square has not been optimally utilized both in terms of function and available facilities, is not architecturally aesthetic and does not support an ecological environment.

A. Suggestions

Seeing the current conditions, it is necessary to improve the town square area, by creating an integrated area design concept, which includes:

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